

**Circular
Cities & Regions
Initiative**

Knowledge Hub

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D1.4 Clustering activities

WP 1, T 1.6

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Technical references

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

D1.4 Clustering Activities describes the clustering activities with other EU projects selected under the CircBio 01-1 during the first 18 months of the CCRI Knowledge Hub project (January 2024 to June 2025). These activities have been implemented in close collaboration with the CCRI Coordination and Support Office (CCRI-CSO) and under the guidelines of DG Research and Innovation (RTD) within the scope of the activities committed in our Grant Agreement (GA).

Key findings and lessons learnt

- Close communication and the use of common tools with the **1st level** helped to clarify roles, align resources, and avoid duplication of activities.
- Cities, regions and projects on circular economy need a payback in form of knowledge, resources, or services to see the benefits or being involved in a new network. Now that the CCRI Knowledge Hub has content and services to offer, the **3rd level** will be prioritised in terms of engagement.

Challenges encountered & mitigation measures

- According to the conversations with REA and CCRI-CSO, the CCRI knowledge hub activities should be addressed to engage newcomers to the CCRI, so no activities have been promoted with EU CCRI projects (as described in the task).

The lack of own social media and website limits the engagement of new projects. Mitigation measures: efforts have been made through partners' own social media accounts, networking activities in CE events, sending out personalised mailings, among other actions.

Actions implemented with the **1st level** and **3rd level** considering the three levels of collaboration, coordination and cooperation:

- **1st level**
 - Collaboration actions: common call for external experts, ad hoc meetings for technical issues such as the Self-Assessment Tool (SAT), joint social media campaigns, and the organisation of a side event.
 - Coordination: communication requirements established at the beginning of the project, regular meetings among CCRI supporters, on-demand meetings on communication and technological aspects, and coordination tools.
 - Cooperation actions in communication and dissemination content and in the CCRI events.
- **3rd level**: mainly collaboration in events and cooperation in dissemination activities.

Next steps

- **1st level**
 - To organise joint media campaigns and to implement joint or collaborative communication and dissemination actions (WP7).
 - To collaborate in the organisation of events and workshops (WP7 and WP6).
 - To explore the delivery of coordinated outputs with CCRI-CSO, REA, and the sister project, especially related to policy recommendations (WP8).

- To actively participate in CCRI events.
- To continue collaborating, coordinating, and cooperating with CCRI and its supporters by using existing tools and joining coordination meetings and related events (WP1, WP5).
- **3rd level:**
 - To collaborate in the organisation of events and workshops (WP7 and WP6).
 - To identify synergies, exchange good practices, and provide evidence to support EU policy development.
 - To strengthen the network by involving new projects in project actions such as capacity building activities (WP3) — including potential speaker roles — and communication and dissemination events (WP7).
 - To engage new projects identified in the Good Practice analysis and mapping (WP2) in project activities.

1. Introduction

1.1. Project overview

Circular Cities and Regions Initiative Knowledge Hub (CCRI Knowledge Hub) aims to increase the impact of the existing Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI) by enlarging the network of involved stakeholders, bringing together the knowledge and critical mass already developed around Circular Economy (CE) implementation and building upon the CE stakeholder platform. The goal is to promote and make the CE concept a reality in EU cities and regions, particularly those in the early stage of CE transition.

To reach its objective, CCRI Knowledge Hub acts as a “Knowledge Hub”, leveraging existing initiatives and projects to foster the adoption of CE in EU cities and regions. CCRI Knowledge Hub’s formula is based on **three principles**: (a) easy access to systematised workable knowledge; (b) tailored mentoring according to users’ needs; and (c) effective awareness-raising to make the CE more desirable, that build upon **four main dimensions**: (i) Public engagement; (ii) Innovation and technology; (iii) Business models and financial support; and (iv) Impact evaluation.

Figure 1: CCRI Knowledge Hub’s formular

CCRI Knowledge Hub gathers a multidisciplinary expert consortium of 11 partners from 6 EU countries (research and technological centres, universities, research organisations, international networks and associations, regional authorities as well as specialised companies and SMEs) that bring in complementary skills and competences to achieve the project’s objectives.

Project basic data:

- Duration: 1st of January 2024 - 31st of December 2026 (36 months).
- Maximum grant (as stated in the annex 2 of the Grant Agreement, GA): 2.612.932,04€.
- Project number: 101135174
- Call: HORIZON-CL6-2023-CircBio-01-1
- Type of action: Coordination and Support Action (CSA)

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1.2. Delivery purpose & scope

This deliverable aims to describe the clustering activities with other EU projects selected under the CircBio 01-1 during the first 18 months of the project (January 2024 to June 2025). These activities have been implemented in close collaboration with the CCRI Coordination and Support Office (CCRI-CSO) and under the guidelines of DG Research and Innovation (RTD) within the scope of the activities committed in our Grant Agreement (GA). The related task is the task 1.6 “Clustering activities with other EU projects selected under the CircBio 01-1”. In this sense, it is important to note that according to the conversations with REA and CCRI-CSO, the CCRI Knowledge Hub's activities should be addressed at engaging newcomers to the CCRI, so no activities have been addressed to EU CCRI projects (as described in the task) beyond those in which the CCRI knowledge Hub has been invited or are part of the already existing networks.

The D1.4 is a “living document”, thus, its content may be adapted throughout the project duration to reflect changes within the project network coordination procedures. This is a preliminary version submitted in month 18 (June 2025). An updated version will be submitted at the end of the project in month 36 (December 26).

1.3. Target audience

The **main audience of the document** are CCRI Knowledge Hub partners, the RTD and CCRI-CSO, as this deliverable aims to report the clustering activities implemented during the first 18 months of the project and extract lessons learnt and successful procedures to be implemented during the next 18 months of the CCRI Knowledge Hub project. Additionally, this document is listed in the GA as “public”, i.e., it is intended to be made available to a wider audience, including the European Commission (EC) and appointed independent expert reviewers. By being publicly accessible, it ensures transparency and accountability, allowing stakeholders to gain insights into the project's clustering approach and procedures.

1.4. Applicable documents

The following documents have been necessary to develop D1.4 Clustering activities:

- CCRI Knowledge Hub DoA, which is annex 1 to the GA n° 101135174 and contains the details of how the action (project) is being carried out. This document was prepared during the initiating and planning phase of the project.
- CCRI Knowledge Hub D1.1 Project management handbook that describes the different levels of coordination and communication inside and outside the consortium.
- D1.2 Network coordination guidelines 1 that describes the describes the different levels of coordination, cooperation and collaboration between CCRI knowledge Hub and external stakeholders.

1.5. Acronyms

CCRI: Circular cities and regions initiative

CCRI-CSO: Circular cities and regions initiative coordination & support office

CCRI-CSA: Circular cities and regions initiative coordination and support action

CE: Circular Economy

CSA: Coordination and Support Action

EC: European Commission

EIB: European Investment Bank

GA: Grant Agreement

KVC: Kveloce (project coordinator)

RTD: DG Research & Innovation

2. Three levels of coordination

As described in D1.2, to guarantee that the work of CCRI Knowledge Hub complements and enhances the CCRI activities, to avoid repetition and to make the most of the cooperation with other networks/initiatives and available resources, a 3-level “Circular model of Collaboration, Coordination and Cooperation” has been established (Figure 2):

Figure 2: Overview of the 3-level circular model of collaboration, coordination and cooperation

This deliverable is focused on the clustering activities developed under the **1st level** and **3rd level** of collaboration, coordination and cooperation.

The **1st level** of collaboration, coordination and cooperation between the CCRI (EC and RTD), the CCRI-CSO, other projects funded by the topic CircBio 01-1 (the sister project CCRI-CSA), and other CCRI supporters (the EIB and the Circle Economy); to ensure that the objectives are aligned, and the activities are complementary, meaningful, and reinforcing.

The **3rd level** is addressed to the potential new CCRI pilots, fellows, projects, partnering organisations members, and other interested stakeholders; aimed at (i) enlarging the CCRI network with new projects, pilots and fellows, and (ii) complementing the already ongoing activities implemented by the CCRI to ensure and maintain a profiting relationship with the CCRI projects, pilots, fellows and partnering organisation members and other interested stakeholders.

3. Clustering activities in the first 18 months

In the following sections, the common activities implemented to align efforts towards promoting CE in Europe among the entities involved in the **1st level** and **3rd level** of collaboration, coordination and cooperation are described.

3.1. 1st level

3.1.1. Collaboration actions

For collaboration, as described in D1.2, we understand the **common actions defined and agreed upon previously and in continuous dialogue between the 1st level entities**. During the first 18 months of the project the following collaboration activities were implemented:

Participation in the Accelerator session organised in the framework of the World Circular Economy Forum 2024: KVC presented in the Elevator pitches session the services offered by the CCRI knowledge Hub to the CCRI community, the 18th April 2024.

Common call for external experts: A [common call for experts](#) on CE was launched in the summer of 2024 between the CCRI-CSO and the CCRI Knowledge Hub with the supervision of REA (Figure 2). The idea was to have a common pool of external experts to be contracted to deliver the services/mentoring programme offered by both groups. The call was jointly designed, disseminated and evaluated with common templates and ad hoc meetings. Some experts were selected to be part of the pool for both (CCRI-CSO services and CCRI mentoring programme), others just for one, and others rejected. A personalised email was also jointly sent to experts with the corresponding results. The contracting is then managed separately by each organisation according to the needs of the cities/regions supported.

Figure 2: Call for expression of interest (common launched with the CCRI-CSO)

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Self-Assessment Tool (SAT) developed by the CCRI-CSO: Although the SAT was not used as the main basis for the formulation of the current CCRI knowledge Hub support pathways, as described in D3.1, its principles and components remained part of the broader methodological environment in which the project operates. This was the conclusion of some bilateral meetings between the CCRI-CSO and the CCRI knowledge Hub partners in charge of developing the support pathways (UVEG and VTT).

Joint social media campaign between the CCRI-CSO and the CCRI Knowledge Hub: On the occasion of the International Day of Zero Waste, the CCRI Knowledge Hub and the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative collaborated on a joint social media campaign. The campaign featured a carousel of quotes from various stakeholders, each responding to the question: "How does the CCRI Knowledge Hub contribute to achieving a zero-waste future?". The initiative aimed to raise awareness of the CCRI–Knowledge Hub's role in supporting circular economy efforts and to highlight diverse perspectives on its added value for local and regional transitions.

EU Green Week Side Event: The CCRI and CCRI Knowledge Hub hosted a webinar as part of the EU Green Week Side Events on 26 June (Figure 3). The session, titled “*From Practice to Policy: Circular Solutions in Cities and Regions*”, presentations from both initiatives were shared during the session. In particular, the CCRI Knowledge Hub presented its analysis of circular economy projects and initiatives across Europe, highlighting a selection of Good Practices and Less Successful Cases to support knowledge sharing and future replication.

Figure 3: EU Green Week Side Event

26 June 2025
11:00 - 12:30

From Practice to Policy: Circular Solutions in Cities and Regions

AGENDA

Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI) Jan Wynarski - CCRI	11:00 - 11:10
CCRI Knowledge Hub Mireia Ferri - KVelocity	11:10 - 11:20
Analysis of CE projects and initiatives Ana Crespo Cortés - CETEC	11:20 - 11:50
Marketplace of technologies Ana Crespo Cortés - CETEC	11:50 - 12:00
CCRI thematic working groups Andrea Accorigi - CCRI-CSO	12:00 - 12:20
Q&A and final wrap-up Denise Venere - ICONS	12:20 - 12:30

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3.1.2. Coordination tools

According to D1.2, the CCRI Knowledge Hub, the CCRI (REA and EC), the CCRI-CSO and other supporters work in a **coordination pathway to have a common plan of activities and shared responsibilities to avoid duplication** of their work and to advance in a common direction. For that, some communication requirements had been agreed, regular meetings have been organised, on-demand meetings held when needed, and coordination tools established:

Communication requirements: Any exchange of information between the CCRI Knowledge Hub, RTD and CCRI-CSO includes in copy functional mailboxes to guarantee fast response: CCRI-CSO@ecorys.com and CCRIknowledgehub@kveloce.com. For the communication with other supporters, a dedicated list is included in an excel file shared between all the entities.

Regular meetings with REA and CCRI-CSO: The CCRI Knowledge Hub meets monthly with RTD and the CCRI-CSO to update about the progress of the project, discuss potential overlaps and align the strategy. In addition, dedicated meetings for concrete issues arisen during the project implementation have been organised during these first 18th months, as the meetings related to the CCRI knowledge Hub platform integration, with the participation of INVENIAM as the partner in charge of the platform and technical staff from REA, and the meetings to align the project visuals with the CCRI, with the participation of ICONS as leader of the Communication and Dissemination in the CCRI Knowledge Hub.

Regular meetings with CCRI supporters: The CCRI Knowledge Hub meets monthly with the sister project and other CCRI supporters (the EIB and the Circle Economy) in the periodic meetings organised by CCRI-CSO and REA. The aim of these meetings is to update about the progress of the project and align efforts and work.

On-demand meetings: These meetings had been organised to agree on concrete topics. For instance, a common approach to present the good practices elaborated by the EIB and the CCRI Knowledge Hub has been agreed but it is pending to be materialised in terms of common visuals and items/titles.

Coordination tools: A shared tool in Excel format was agreed among supporters aimed to provide a snapshot of the main CCRI support offers and update activities (workshops, mentoring, etc.). Based on this excel, the CCRI-CSO created the CCRI Compass¹ available in the CCRI website to help to understand the “big picture”. A shared space in teams is also available to share documents, mainly for communication purposes.

Previous regular meetings and emails ensured the **close communication** between the entities under the umbrella of the CCRI.

3.1.3. Cooperation actions

Based in the definition established in D1.2, the CCRI Knowledge Hub, the CCRI, the CCRI-CSO and other supporters' cooperation is based on the **creation of synergies between each other, their members, and external stakeholders to achieve the same goal**, which is to accelerate

¹ <https://circular-cities-and-regions.ec.europa.eu/ccri-compass>

the implementation of CE in European cities and regions. The activities implemented in this coordination level are the following:

Cooperation in communication and dissemination content: CCRI Knowledge Hub does not currently have an official website or presence on social media platforms, so all the activities implemented (i.e., monthly specials) are prepared in collaboration with the CCRI-CSO and supervised by REA. All communication actions follow the CCRI communication guide and the CCRI media relations toolkit and are agreed with RTD and CCRI-CSO before publication. Each output undergoes a two-step validation process:

- DG-RTD provides feedback on content
- CCRI-CSO reviews visual identity and coherence

In line with the CCRI branding strategy, external communications consistently refer to the project as the “CCRI Knowledge Hub” (the acronym “CCRI-KH” is used only internally). Additionally, the CCRI website, newsletter and social media channels (e.g., LinkedIn) serve as the primary access points for all public communications related to the Knowledge Hub. A shared editorial calendar and regular emails exchange ensure streamlined planning.

Cooperation in the CCRI events: members of the CCRI Knowledge Hub participated actively in the last two CCRI events solving doubts and fostering networking in the CCRI stand. Moreover, our most advanced mentees were invited to workshops organised by the CCRI-CSO following the CCRI-CSO requests.

This ongoing collaboration helps keep all communication consistent and aligned with the overall message of the CCRI. While the CCRI Knowledge Hub consortium remains responsible for producing the content, coordination with DG RTD and the CCRI-CSO will continue throughout the duration of the project to ensure coherence and visibility.

3.2. 3rd level

According to the conversations with REA and CCRI-CSO, as described in D1.2, the focus of the CCRI Knowledge Hub is to complement the support already provided by the CCRI-CSO to pilots, fellows and projects with the planned services and to enlarge the existing network. That is the reason why our activities had been focused on these two main objectives inside the collaboration and cooperation levels. At this stage, activities under the coordination level had not been implemented, but will be considered in the next report.

3.2.1. Collaboration actions

Collaboration in events: On 13th June 2024, the CCRI Knowledge Hub took part in the panel discussion titled “*Closing the Loop: Circular Economy, a Key Factor for Sustainability*” at the EBN Congress² in Nantes, France. During the session, the Knowledge Hub presented the project’s activities to an audience of over 70 participants.

² <https://www.ebncongress.eu/schedule2024>

Members of the CCRI Knowledge Hub participated actively in meetings of CCRI projects such as A2C³ and CIRCS⁴ (two in the case of CIRCSYST project). It is worth mentioning that in the last workshop organised by CIRCSYST in Valencia the 29th May 2025, members of the CCRI knowledge Hub presented the Knowledge Hub and the upcoming call for cities and regions in relation to the mentoring programme.

3.2.2. Cooperation actions

Cooperation in dissemination: some CCRI projects contributed to disseminating the CCRI Knowledge Hub call for experts and the expression of interest to cities and regions for our mentoring programme. Some of the projects that contributed to the dissemination of both calls were: A2C, HOOP, ViSS, BIO2REG, and Frontsh1p; some of them part of the LOOP cluster.

Cooperation with RESOURCE project: KVC participated in one of the in-person meetings of the project RESOURCE⁵ - REgional project development aSsistance fOr the Uptake of an aRagonese Circular Economy- funded by Horizon Europe, on June 2024. The reason was to explore if the methodology developed in the project to select good practices could be applicable to the CCRI Knowledge Hub project (task under the WP2). In addition, KVC had different online meetings with the responsible of this task to deep on the criteria. RESOURCE criteria to select good practices was based on geographical coverage, replicability and long-term sustainability. However, and according to the CCRI Knowledge Hub design, these criteria were not used as main criteria in our project as the main criteria were based on the four project domains (public engagement, impact assessment, technology and business). But some of the criteria were considered to describe the good practices selected, for instance: scalability, replicability and transferability (section 6 of the good practices report).

Cooperation in capacity building activities: CCRI knowledge Hub organised a total of 9 workshops in the first reporting period. In some of them, projects funded under the CircBio and beyond were invited to share their experiences and lessons learnt with cities and regions participating in the workshops. Below a table summarises the projects invited as speakers in the workshops organised as part of the capacity building activities:

Table 1: Cooperation in the capacity building activities

Workshop	Place (mentee) and date	CE projects invited as speakers
Public Engagement in Circular Economy Initiatives – KVC workshop	Valencia 19/09/2024	FRONTSH1P - A FRONTrunner approach to Systemic circular, Holistic & Inclusive solutions for a New Paradigm of territorial circular economy ⁶ funded by the H2020 programme.

³ <https://agro2circular.eu/>

⁴ <https://circsyst.eu/>

⁵ <https://resource-invest.eu/>

⁶ <https://frontsh1p.eu/>

		<p>RESOURCE*- REgional project development aSsistance fOr the Uptake of an aRagonese Circular Economy ⁷ - funded by Horizon Europe programme.</p> <p>EcoeFISHent – Demonstrable and replicable cluster implementing systemic solutions through multilevel circular value chains for eco-efficient valorisation of fishing and fist industries side-streams⁸ - funded by the H2020 programme.</p> <p>CityLoops – Closing the loop for urban materials flows⁹- funded by H2020 programme.</p> <p>BIO2REG*- Enabling transition towards circular and systemic BIOeconomy model regions by a Regions-to-Regions approach ¹⁰ funded by Horizon Europe programme.</p> <p>A climate shelter on the roof of a house for homeless, local project funded by the Valencia city council.</p>
Circular Economy and Agri-food - UVEG workshop	Valencia 20/09/2024	A2C – Territorial circular systemic solution for the upcycling of residues from the agrifood sector ¹¹ - funded by H2020 programme.
Building Circular Future: Exploring Material Hubs – ICONS workshop	Online (Møre og Romsdal) 25/03/2025	WoodCircles* – Integrated, circular, and digital supported sustainable solutions for waste minimisation and carbon capture in buildings and the construction sector ¹² – co-founded by the Horizon Europe programme
EU project pills: I3 instrument – EBN workshop	Online (Skive) 07/05/2025	CESAM – Circular Economy and Sustainable solutions for agrifood in the Mediterranean – co-funded by the CE (I3 managed by ESMEA).

⁷ <https://resource-invest.eu/>

⁸ <https://ecoeffishent.eu/>

⁹ <https://cityloops.eu/>

¹⁰ <https://bio2reg.eu/>

¹¹ <https://agro2circular.eu/es/>

¹² <https://woodcircles.eu/>

Enhancing Public Engagement in Circular Transitions – ALDA workshop	Online (Poltava) 19/05/2025	Take a step! Sustainable territories & European Participation ¹³ Project co-funded by the EU under the “citizens’ voice how to get engaged on EU values and policies” and promoted by ALDA. ERICA ¹⁴ – Environment monitoring through civic engagement – project funded by the Erasmus + programme
Circular Economy, stakeholder workshop – FILSE workshop	Online (Gacko) 28/05/2025	P.Ri.S.Ma. MED2 – Piano Rifiuti e Scarti in Mare di pesca, acquacoltura e diporto nel Mediterraneo – fase 2 ¹⁵ [waste management and marine discarding plan from fishing, aquaculture and recreational fishing in the Mediterranean – phase 2] funded by the Interreg programme.
Plastics in agriculture – CETEC workshop	Online (Stavenger) 06/05/2025	PHAntastic – PHA-based iNnovative agriculTurAI solutions to deliver bio-based ferTILisers and plant protection produCts ¹⁶ – funded by the Horizon Europe programme. ViSS – Viable, safe and sustainable PHBV value chain for food packaging applications ¹⁷ – funded by Horizon European programme.
Sustainable Glass Reuse in the EU: Policy, Regional Case Studies and opportunities – INVENIAM workshop	Online (Montpellier) 05/06/2025	EU4CELC - EU4 Circular Economy and Livable Cities project co-financed by the EU and BMZ (the Federal Ministry for Economic Cooperation and Development in Germany).

NOTE: projects funded by the CIRC BIO calls had been identified by an *

The agenda and explanation of each workshop is detailed in the annexes of the D3.3 Delivery of the first services (1st 18 months of the project).

¹³ <https://www.piccionaia.org/take-a-step-sustainable-territories/>

¹⁴ <https://www.ericaproject.eu/>

¹⁵ <https://interreg-marittimo.eu/es/web/p.ri.s.ma.-med2>

¹⁶ <https://phantastic-project.eu/>

¹⁷ <https://viss-project.eu/>

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3.2.3. Additional actions to enlarge the network

In addition, to enlarge the network, projects analysed as part of the CCRI Knowledge Hub activities (WP2) and cities/regions who submitted their expression of interest to receive our mentoring programme (WP3) were included in our mailing list to:

- Invite them to the workshops/capacity building activities organised as part of the support pathways on different topics around CE.
- Share with them the recordings of the workshops and key take aways.
- Invite them to workshops/webinars organised to share the CCRI Knowledge Hub results.

NOTE: CCRI Knowledge Hub does not have its own social media nor newsletters.

4. Conclusions and next steps

D1.4 contain a description of the clustering activities with other EU projects selected under the CircBio 01-1 and beyond during the first 18 months of the project and other CCRI supporters (**1st level**) as well as clustering activities with other CE projects (**3rd level**). The activities reported in this deliverable follow the three level of collaboration, coordination and cooperation described in D1.2 to be aligned with the CCRI.

After 18 months of project implementation, the following **conclusions** are reached:

- Successful collaboration, coordination and cooperation measures and actions had been implemented in the **1st level**. In this sense, close communication and common tools to map actions and plans among supporters had been key to clarify roles, align resources and not overlap activities.
- Now that the project has content to be shared derived from WP2 (knowledge and resource building) and WP3 (preparation of customised support services, capacity building and first delivery of services), more efforts can be put in the collaboration, coordination and cooperation measures and actions with the **3rd level**.
- The lack of own social media and website limits the engagement of new projects, although efforts have been made through partners' own social media accounts, networking activities in CE events, sending out personalised mailings, and the like.

As **next steps**, the following are agreed among partners in relation to the **1st level** and **3rd level** and the different levels of collaboration, coordination and cooperation:

Table 2: Plan for the upcoming clustering activities

	1st level	3 rd level
Collaboration	To organise joint media campaigns (WP7). To collaborate in events/workshops organisation (WP7 and WP6).	
Coordination	To explore the delivery of coordinated deliverables with CCRI-CSO, REA and the sister project related to policy recommendations (WP8).	
Cooperation	Communication and Dissemination actions. Active participation in the CCRI events.	Active participation in CE events. To dinamyse the network with new projects inviting them to project actions: capacity building activities (WP3) – also as potential speakers -

		and communication & dissemination events (WP7).
All levels	To continue collaborating, cooperating and coordinating activities with the CCRI and its supporters, using existing tools and participating in coordinating meetings and related events (WP1).	To engage in the project activities new projects identified from the Good Practice analysis and mapping exercise (WP2).

